

THE SQUARES IN THE SMARANDACHE HIGHER POWER PRODUCT SEQUENCES

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Abstract . In this paper we prove that the Smarandache higher power product sequences of the first kind and the second kind do not contain squares.

Key words . Smarandache product sequence, higher power, square.

Let r be a positive integer with $r > 3$, and let $A(n)$ be the n -th power of degree r . Further, let

$$(1) \quad p(n) = \prod_{k=1}^n A(k)+1$$

and

$$(2) \quad Q(n) = \prod_{k=1}^n A(k)-1.$$

Then the sequences $P = \{P(n)\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ and $Q = \{Q(n)\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ are called the Smarandache higher power product sequences of the first kind and the second kind respectively. In this paper we consider the squares in P and Q . We prove the following result.

Theorem . For any positive integer r with $r > 3$, the sequences P and Q do not contain squares.

Proof . By (1), if $P(n)$ is a square, then we have

$$(3) \quad (n!)^r + 1 = a^2,$$

where a is a positive integer. It implies that the equation

$$(4) \quad x^m+1=y^2, \quad m>3$$

has a positive integer solution $(x,y,m)=(n!,a,r)$. However, by the result of [1], the equation (4) has no positive integer solution (x,y,m) . Thus, the sequence P does not contain squares.

Similarly, by (2), if $Q(n)$ is a square, then we have

$$(5) \quad (n!)^r-1=a^2,$$

where a is a positive integer. It implies that the equation

$$(6) \quad x^m-1=y^2, m>3.$$

has a positive integer solution $(x,y,m)=(n!,a,r)$. However, by the result of [2], it is impossible. Thus, the sequence Q does not contain squares. The theorem is proved.

References

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